

INTERNAL FACTORS AFFECTING THE MARKETING STRATEGY OF THE ENTERPRISE "STEKLOPLASTIK" LLC

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Abstract. This article describes the effective management and development of enterprise activities. Receiving individual orders and ordering production, the company's competitive capabilities, financial activity was considered.

Keywords: marketing strategy, factor, order, activity, competition, market, customer.

Structural restructuring and modernization of the economy requires radical improvement and development of existing management approaches, methodologies and methods. Such a requirement is an important task not only for large industrial enterprises, but also for other enterprises and organizations in all fields. Therefore, there is a need for strategic research of management systems in organizations, their in-depth analysis and extensive use of modern scientific achievements in their improvement. The use of strategic marketing methodology, which is one of the newest directions of marketing science, is of particular importance in the implementation of prospective management.

Along with external factors affecting the strategic situation of the enterprise, a number of internal factors are also of great importance. If we have analyzed the factors of the external environment in previous studies, now we need to study the factors of its internal environment.

In particular, the internal factors influencing the determination of the strategy of "Stekloplastik" LLC directly depend on a number of factors that make up its activity. (Figure 1).

1 – picture. Marketing strategy of "Stekloplastik" LLC influencing internal factors.

Organization of production. The volume of products produced at "Stekloplastik" LLC is determined, on the one hand, by the demand for it, and on the other hand, by the availability of production capacities for its production. The organization of production in the society is well established, and today, as we mentioned above, more than 400 types of products are produced in 8 product groups. Great attention is paid to the quality and modernity of every manufactured product. ISO 9001:2000 Quality Management System has been introduced in the enterprise to improve the quality of manufactured products.

At "Stekloplastik" LLC more than 90 types of manufactured products are included in the localization program, and the reduction of the tax burden on these types of products will directly affect the value of the enterprise.

Leadership. This factor of production has a great impact on the value of the enterprise. At "Stekloplastik" LLC the manager of the enterprise, the chairman of the control board ensure the effective management and development of the enterprise. This fact must be taken into account during the evaluation process, in particular, when calculating the discount rates, because in the event that the enterprise is sold, its plans for its future activities may change. Director of Society and Deputy Director of External Economic Relations, Deputy Director of Merchandise Distribution, Deputy Director of Production and Deputy Director of General Affairs form the management of "Stekloplastik" LLC.

Every level of leadership is important in creating enterprise value. Every leader should have the qualities of leadership, communication, oratory and foresight. These characteristics are embodied in the chairman of the supervisory board, the highest leader of "Stekloplastik" LLC, under whose leadership all employees obey and work together. Such a chain of management helps to eliminate all errors and shortcomings, and this is a factor that helps to increase production, increase labor productivity, increase the potential of the enterprise, and directly increase the value of the enterprise.

Contracts with customers. As we know, it is the turnover that determines and creates the main value of any enterprise. Until today these state programs and tender sales have been creating the movement of goods of "Stekloplastik" LLC. "Stekloplastik" LLC has a number of objective reasons for good work with customers, especially the population. First of all, the distance of this enterprise from the city center, the main factor in fully satisfying the needs of each customer is time and convenience. "Stekloplastik" LLC is located 25 km from the city center, which poses a serious threat to meet the needs of customers at an excellent level. Secondly, the inability to be aware of bank account information in a timely manner, the delay of payments as a result of the influence of the above-mentioned factor when working with the bank. Thirdly, the imperfection of the mechanism for accepting individual orders and ordering production. Fourth, after the contracts are signed, payments are delayed by the customer and the company also delays the delivery of goods. Such shortcomings have a serious impact on the decrease in the value of "Stekloplastik" LLC.

Personnel capacity. The need to assess the value of personnel potential comes from the conclusion that people in any enterprise are an important factor, like all other economic resources (raw materials, means of production, fixed and circulating capital, information, technology, etc.).

The quality of labor resources has a direct impact on the company's competitive capabilities and is one of the important areas of creating competitive advantages. The concept of "human resources" is involved as a theoretical basis of new economic forms of working with personnel.

The essence of this concept is the application of economic criteria in relation to the assessment of the role of the human factor in production, organization and management, as well as in the construction of the entire system of personnel work.

The concept of "human resources" is based on the possibility of applying economic estimates of people's ability to generate a certain income. The higher the individual productivity of an employee's work and the longer his period of activity lasts, the more he earns and the more valuable he is to the enterprise. In general, the employees of "Stekloplastik" LLC were selected, and the employees with high labor productivity were left, and their period of activity continues for a long time.

Personnel capacity should be understood as the sum of the skills and capabilities of personnel to ensure the effective operation of the enterprise. According to its nature, essence and content, human resources are among the intangible assets of the enterprise. At the same time, it cannot be included in the sentence of intellectual property, because by its nature this potential is changeable, does not have legal protection and cannot be alienated or sold for exclusive use of certain people, 80% of the employees and workers working in "Stekloplastik" LLC work in their specialties. This situation cannot be called a negative situation, but the change of this percentage can increase the value of the enterprise, causing a negative or positive change.

Financial activity. Financial activity of factories also forms the value of the enterprise, as well as production activity. In 2022, "Stekloplastik" LLC had securities worth 98 million soums, 96 billion soums. other long-term financial investments amounting to 209 billion soums. made short-term investments of 2,344 million soums from the total financial activity. received an income of soms and has a positive effect on the formation of the society's value.

All of the above factors In the following table, we can see the positive or negative impact on the value of "Stekloplastik" LLC in its further activities.

In conclusion, Internal factors affecting the value of "Stekloplastik" LLC, the enterprise itself has a positive opportunity for its own benefit. External factors directly affect the value of the enterprise under the influence of the government and the market. For this, the enterprise itself must adapt to the external environment.

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